

Herbal Remedies for Mental Health Disorders: A Focus on Adaptogenic Plants and Their Mechanisms of Action

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Abstract: Adaptogenic plants are increasingly being recognized as potential therapeutic agents in the treatment of mental health disorders. In this review, we summarized current evidence of their efficacy, safety, and mechanisms of action in the treatment of mental health disorders. The findings of the clinical studies showed that adaptogens, such as ashwagandha, Rhodiola, and holy basil, are effective in alleviating the symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression, with a good safety profile and minimal side effects. Adaptogenic plants exert their effects through several mechanisms of action, including modulation of the stress response systems, neuroprotection, and anti-inflammatory effects. However, challenges remain in standardizing adaptogenic plant extracts and dosage forms and in clinical studies to analyze the interactions with other pharmaceuticals. In light of these challenges, adaptogenic plants represent a promising alternative to conventional pharmacotherapy for a wide range of mental health disorders, with probable lower side effects and greater accessibility. From a clinical practice perspective, there are promising prospects for the potential of these herbal remedies in the treatment of mental health disorders for the augmentation of treatment options and for better outcomes. Further research is warranted to optimize the therapeutic regimens and to integrate these remedies into comprehensive paradigms of mental health care.

Keywords: Adaptogenic plants, mental health, herbal remedies, clinical trials, mechanisms of action.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental health disorders are a critical global health issue that does not discriminate in terms of age, race, and socio-economic status and affects people worldwide. Depression, anxiety, and stress-related disorders not only affect overall functioning but also represent massive fiscal burdens on health systems globally. The World Health Organization underscores the fact that nearly 264 million individuals in the world are affected by depression, and anxiety disorders represent the most common mental health disorders worldwide [1]. Despite conventional treatment options, such as psychotherapy and pharmacological therapy, several barriers continue to impede access to proper care, including financial constraints, lack of availability, stigma in society, and fears of adverse side effects. This lack of access to mental health care underscores the urgent need for alternative and complementary therapeutic options.

Herbal remedies have been used for millennia across cultures as part of the healing arts for both physical and mental disorders [2]. Herbalism, or phytotherapy, is a use of plants and plant-based derivatives as therapeutic remedies and constitutes ancient knowledge passed down from one generation to another. Herbal remedies have also had a significant role in the treatment of anxiety, depression, and other mood disorders [2]. In fact, herbal preparations containing St. John's Wort (*Hypericum perforatum*), Valerian (*Valeriana officinalis*), and Passionflower (*Passiflora incarnata*) have traditionally been used to induce relaxation, improve sleep, and reduce symptoms of mild to moderate anxiety and depression. Additionally, plant extracts like Kava (*Piper methysticum*) have shown promise in the treatment of anxiety and stress-related disorders. The historical and cultural significance of herbal remedies in mental health reaffirms the persistence of appeal and potential therapeutic value of plant-based therapies [2].

Whereas pharmaceutical medicines are still developing and being very much used today in modern medicine, herbs are considered holistically to health and wellness, in treating both symptoms and the underlying imbalances in the body that lead to psychopathologies [2]. Unlike the conventional pharmacotherapeutic approach, which targets specific neurotransmitter pathways or symptoms, herbal medicines engage multiple physiological systems involved in stress and regulation of emotions. As a class of botanicals, adaptogenic herbs, as stated, enhance resistance to stress and promote overall well-being by balancing HPA, the sympathetic nervous system, and other pathways sensitive to stress [3]. This aligns with the biopsychosocial approach since it identifies and harmonizes the interaction and relevance of biological, psychological, and social factors on health outcomes. Given the complexity of the interplay between physiological, psychological, and environmental factors in mental health, herbal remedies allow comprehensive mental health care that transcends symptomatic expression.

Within the field of herbal medicine, adaptogenic plants have shown high promise in mental health and generally to provide general resilience. Adaptogens are a group of herbs and botanicals defined to be those that help the body adapt to stress, physical or mental, and to homeostasis and resilience of the body. They have the capacity to modulate the body's stress response systems, encompassing the HPA axis, the sympathetic nervous system, and various neurotransmitter pathways [3]. Thus, adaptogens might provide a natural and effective way to manage symptoms of mental disorders. The preliminary evidence supports the use of adaptogenic plants, such as Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*), Rhodiola (*Rhodiola rosea*), and Holy Basil (*Ocimum sanctum*) to exert anxiolytic, antidepressant, and mood-stabilizing effects, promising candidates for further investigation and clinical use [4].

This study seeks to consider potential effects in multiple aspects, starting from efficacy and safety to a holistic approach to wellness, as an alternative treatment strategy for mental health disorders [5]. In fact, the plants in question work through multifaceted mechanisms within the body, rectifying underlying imbalances in the body and promoting overall resilience. These plants are in general well-tolerated and have a low risk of adverse effects, and therefore suitable for treatment for long periods or integration into a holistic treatment program. Furthermore, herbal medicine allows for a personal approach that consults individual constitution, lifestyle, and health conditions, thus being a suitable treatment for months or years and integrating into a holistic treatment program. Therefore, an investigation of the potential of adaptogenic plants in mental health disorders seeks to add another alternative to the array of treatment options available for mental health disorders, providing safe, accessible, and gentler alternatives to conventional pharmacotherapy [2]. Through rigorous scientific inquiry and clinical investigation, the

scientist may continue to uncover mechanisms of action, efficacy, and safety profiles of adaptogenic plants, guiding their integration into evidence-based practices in mental health care.

II. MAJOR MENTAL HEALTH DISORDERS

Mental health disorders, collectively, refer to diseases that are defined by impairments in the functioning of an individual's mood, thoughts, and behavior. These impairments can range from mild to severe and can be debilitating to an individual's quality of life, relationships, and overall well-being. In this response, we will discuss some of the most prevalent mental health disorders—including depression, anxiety, and PTSD—provide a general overview of their prevalence and symptoms.

Depression is a mood disorder, characterized by persistent experiences of sadness, hopelessness, and a lack of interest or pleasure in activities [6]. It affects people of all ages, sex, and backgrounds and is one of the main causes of disability throughout the world. Depression symptoms may range from mild to severe and last for varying periods of time and often damage an individual's quality of life and functioning. The most common form of depression, MDD, is typically experienced with symptoms, which include fatigue, changes in appetite or weight, sleep disturbances, and thoughts of self-harm or suicide [6]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 1 in every 8 individuals, or 970 million people worldwide, suffered from a mental condition in 2019, with anxiety and depression being the most frequent [1].

Anxiety disorders are a class of mental disorders characterized by excessive worry, fear, or apprehension about a situation or situations that are out of proportion to the situation and interfere with daily function [7]. The most common anxiety disorders include GAD, panic disorder, social anxiety disorder, and specific phobias. Symptoms may include restlessness and irritability, muscle tension, difficulty in concentration [7]. Anxiety disorders can be so debilitating that the ability to function in social, occupational, and other domains of life is significantly impaired. According to the World Health Organization, 301 million individuals worldwide suffered from anxiety disorders in 2019, making them the most frequent of all mental diseases [1].

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) is a mental disorder that may occur as a result of exposure to or witnessing a traumatic event, such as a natural disaster or other disaster, war, or physical assault [8]. The symptoms of PTSD include the re-experience of the traumatic event through flashbacks, nightmares, and intrusive memories. PTSD victims will avoid situations or people that will remind them of the traumatic event, have mood swings, and experience difficulty with concentration [8]. According to the National Institute of Mental Health, almost 6.8% of adults living in the United States will develop PTSD at some point in their lives [9]. Statistically, PTSD is diagnosed in 8% of adolescents aged 13-18 years, while an estimate states that in a lifetime, 1 out of 11 will be diagnosed with PTSD [9]. Women are twice as likely as men to suffer from PTSD, and certain ethnic groups, such as U.S. Latinos, African Americans, and Native Americans/Alaska Natives, are disproportionately affected [9]. The prevalence of PTSD varies by country: The number of cases is greater in high-income countries than in upper-middle and lower-middle income countries. One such study shows that the number of cases in high-income countries is 5.0%, which is greater than that of upper-middle countries at 2.3% and lower-middle countries at 2.1% [10].

Schizophrenia affects 24 million people or 1 in 300 people throughout the world [11]. People with schizophrenia die on average 10-20 years earlier than the general population [12]. Schizophrenia is associated with considerable impairments in perception and changes in behavior. Symptoms may include persistent delusions, hallucinations, disorganized thinking, highly disorganized behavior, or extreme agitation. People with schizophrenia commonly experience persistent difficulties with their cognitive functioning [11]. However, a range of effective treatment options exist, including medication, psychoeducation, family interventions, and psychosocial rehabilitation.

II.I Limitations of conventional treatments:

Major mental health disorders, such as depression, anxiety, and PTSD, are prevalent and may be disabling to the individual. The conventional treatments include antidepressants and psychotherapy;

however, these interventions have been very limited and have provided an opportunity to seek alternative therapies, such as those achieved with herbal medications.

One of the most important limitations of these conventional treatments has been their inconsistent efficiency [13]. For example, a meta-analysis performed on antidepressant drugs showed that only 40% of patients diagnosed with MDD attained remission after 12 weeks of treatment [13]. This indicates a real need for alternative treatments that may exhibit a more consistent response for patients who have mental illness.

Other limitations in conventional treatments include side effects and relapse [14]. For instance, antidepressants may bring in side effects such as weight gain, sexual dysfunction, and insomnia. In addition, withdrawal of antidepressants may entail relapse, a terrible fact for the patients that needs restarting the treatment. Herbal medicines, especially adaptogenic plants, may be the safer and more tolerable alternative for the treatment of mental disorders because they are seen as natural and free from the side effects attached to conventional treatments.

In addition, conventional treatments are expensive and not available to everyone [15]. For example, in the United States, the cost of antidepressant medication can be pretty steep, so some are turned to other forms of treatment. Herbal remedies are cheaper and more accessible, hence are more viable options for an individual who cannot afford the traditional treatments.

In summary, although conventional therapy is effective for some patients with mental disorders, there is a shortcoming in terms of inconsistency of efficacy, side effects, and the risk of relapse. These encouraged researchers to investigate alternative treatments, particularly adaptogenic plants and their herbal application. As research continues to find the mechanism of action and the safety of these herbs, they may provide a more tolerable and accessible alternative for the management of mental disorders.

III. ADAPTOGENIC PLANTS

Adaptogenic plants are a unique kind of botanical remedies, famous for their unique ability to help the body adapt to stressors and promote health. The term "adaptogen" was first defined by Russian scientist Dr. Nikolai Lazarev in 1940s and describes substances that increase the body's resistance to stress and normalize physiological functions without disturbing normal bodily processes [16]. Adaptogens have a few major characteristics that distinguish them from any other herbs and botanicals. The first feature is that adaptogens are absolutely non-toxic and safe for long-term use, and there is a very low risk for adverse effects even at very high doses. Adaptogens also have a non-specific mode of action; that means they have a balancing effect on many physiological systems but don't selectively attack any given symptoms or organs. In fact, this general activity allows adaptogens to regulate the body's stress response mechanisms, including the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, the sympathetic nervous system, and several neurotransmitter pathways, thus promoting the resilience and homeostasis [17].

Adaptogenic plants possess the outstanding ability to increase the body's ability to withstand stress and attain balance in physiological processes. Therefore, they make precious allies in the support of well-being. One of the defining characteristics of adaptogens is their ability to manifest a "two-way" control influence on the body, that is, they can either stimulate or dampen physiological functions as necessary to achieve homeostasis [16]. This two-way approach makes adaptogens very versatile therapeutics, as it allows them to meet the specific needs of every individual. Besides, adaptogens have a hormetic effect, meaning they have beneficial effects at suboptimal doses, while, at optimal doses, they become less effective or even toxic. This hormetic effect is of significance for safety and efficacy of adaptogens, as it prevents overdose or toxicity while still reaching therapeutic benefits [16]. Overall, adaptogenic plants take the natural and holistic view toward the body's resilience to stress and well-being support.

III.I Examples of commonly used adaptogenic plants

i) Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*):

Ashwagandha, also known as *Withania somnifera*, is a famed adaptogenic herb with deep roots in Ayurvedic medicine. Its adaptogenic properties arise from its ability to modulate the body's stress response systems, mainly by lowering cortisol levels—the main stress hormone [18]. Cortisol is essential in the body's fight-or-flight response to stress. Prolonged elevations of cortisol can lead to a range of health problems, including anxiety, depression, and impaired immune function. The mechanism by which ashwagandha functions as an adaptogen is regulating the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, which regulates the body's stress response, and the maintenance of homeostasis within the nervous and endocrine systems [18].

Ashwagandha also has anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory actions that add to its adaptogenic effects [19]. These additional therapeutic actions contribute to ashwagandha's overall health and well-being. As it decreases inflammation, neutralizes free radicals, and modulates the immune function, the use of ashwagandha is recognized not only for its stress-reducing actions but also for its ability to improve vitality and promote longevity. Therefore, ashwagandha is valued not only for its stress-reducing potential but also for its potential to improve the overall health and longevity of the body.

ii). Rhodiola (*Rhodiola rosea*):

Rhodiola, also referred to as *Rhodiola rosea*, is one of the most adaptogenic herbs, native to mountainous regions of Europe, Asia, and North America. Rhodiola has enjoyed centuries-old prestige for its adaptogenic properties and has been used by various cultures that give it great importance for mental and physical endurance, mood uplifting, and fatigue-reducing capabilities [20]. Research indicates that adaptogenic properties of rhodiola are exerted via different mechanisms, with the most important being the regulation of neurotransmitter levels in the brain [20]. Serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine are among the neurotransmitters of neurotransmitter systems in the brain that Rhodiola modulates, thereby improving the sense of well-being and resilience to stress, enabling individuals to better cope with hard life situations [21].

Rhodiola is also associated with mitochondrial function modulation. It optimizes the function of this organelle in the body, which is responsible for producing energy. By doing so, Rhodiola boosts the body's ability to produce energy efficiently, which in turn leads to an improvement in energy levels and overall vitality [20]. This double effect on neurotransmitter regulation and mitochondrial function emphasizes that rhodiola is capable of enhancing physical and mental performance, which is why it has attracted quite much attention in traditional and modern medicine for possible therapeutic properties affecting health and vitality.

iii). Ginseng (*Panax ginseng*):

Ginseng, scientifically known as *Panax ginseng*, is a highly valued adaptogenic herb with roots steeped in East Asian tradition, primarily in Korea, China, and Siberia. The varied therapeutic effects of ginseng have made it a staple ingredient of traditional Chinese medicine for hundreds of years. It is regarded as one of the most revered because of its ability to enhance vitality, increase energy levels, and enhance resistance to stress [22]. The heart of ginseng's adaptogenic power lies in the deep reservoir of bioactive compounds known as ginsenosides. Such compounds are believed to be the reason why ginseng is considered adaptogenic. Studies have shown that ginseng might have an adaptogenic effect by modulating the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis; this is an important regulatory system controlling the body's response to stressors [22]. By modulating the HPA axis, ginseng helps in enhancing the body's resistance to stress, and this, in turn, promotes greater well-being and overall resilience [22].

In addition, ginseng has also drawn attention for its potential cognitive properties. Studies have shown that the use of ginseng supplementation may have positive effects on cognitive function: memory, attention, and executive function [22]. Since cognitive function is mostly compromised during times of high-level stress, this fact further epitomizes the adaptogenic properties of ginseng. Moreover, ginseng is

available in myriad forms to suit the individual's preference and needs. Be it in the form of fresh or dried roots, or even in extracts or capsules, ginseng provides a versatile and easily accessible way for one to tap into its adaptogenic properties. In essence, ginseng is a revered botanical ally: it aids in supporting vitality, energy, resilience, and cognitive function, making it a rich and precious addition to the holistic health and well-being practices of people across cultures and generations.

iv). Holy basil (*Ocimum sanctum*):

Holy basil, also known as Tulsi in the Hindu tradition, *Ocimum sanctum* is considered sacred, and its therapeutic properties are attributed to Ayurvedic medicine. Holy basil, which is native to India and other areas of Southeast Asia, has long been venerated for its ability to promote health, energy, and reduce stress [23]. Loaded with a cacophony of phytochemicals, including eugenol, rosmarinic acid, and ocimunosides, holy basil has a large battery of bioactive compounds that work in concert to confer upon holy basil its outstanding adaptogenic properties, which help the body adjust to stress and inhibit its effects [23]. Studies have suggested that holy basil may help regulate cortisol, the major stress hormone, thereby achieving a balanced stress response and well-being in terms of emotions [23].

Moreover, Holy basil has also been reported to impact mood and enhance cognitive enhancement, and therefore, it could be a potent ally in managing stress and supporting mental health generally [24]. All told, holy basil is a precious botanical gem that has been revered for its capacity to imbue vitality, resilience, and serenity in the midst of life's challenges, making it an indispensable component of holistic wellness practices grounded in ancient wisdom.

v). Maca (*Lepidium meyenii*):

Maca, scientifically known as *Lepidium meyenii*, is regarded as a highly revered botanical treasure that is native to the rugged highlands of the Andean range in Peru. Often referred to as "Peruvian ginseng," maca has indisputably set its footprints into the annals of traditional Andean medicine for its purported aphrodisiac qualities and esteemed adaptogenic properties. Well-endowed with a myriad of bioactive compounds—such as macamides and macaenes—maca emerges as a potent reservoir of adaptogenic strength [25]. These bioactive compounds act synergistically to provide maca its honored adaptogenic strength, enabling the body to adapt to and fight off the deleterious effects of stress. There are indications that maca holds promise in boosting energy levels, elevating mood, and bolstering endurance, making it a formidable ally in the realm of vitality and resistance [25]. Quite versatile, maca finds itself incorporated into many culinary preparations, often gracing smoothies and beverages as well as culinary dishes with its unique flavor and potent adaptogenic benefits. In essence, maca emerges as a revered botanical treasure, celebrated for its promise of rejuvenation of the body, elevation of mood, and the fortification of resilience in the face of life's mélange of challenges.

vi). Siberian ginseng (*Eleutherococcus senticosus*):

Siberian ginseng, scientifically known as *Eleutherococcus senticosus*, is a hardy botanical ally that comes from the rugged landscapes of Siberia and Northeast Asia. It has been venerated by traditional Chinese medicine practitioners and Russian folk medicine for centuries, revered for its multi-faceted therapeutic properties. Esteemed for its role in recharging stamina, strengthening immunity, and being resilient to stress, Siberian ginseng is a staunch sentinel of vitality and health [26]. At its core, this adaptogen owes much to its troop of bioactive compounds called eleutherosides, which modulate the body's stress response system. These eleutherosides work in tandem to help the body adapt and cope with stress, bringing it closer to a state of balance and strength [27].

One of the main properties of Siberian ginseng is its promise in boosting physical and mental performance and thus giving relief from fatigue. Physical endurance improves, cognition is sharpened, and fatigue is relieved through the use of these herbs [27]. Because of these properties, Siberian ginseng becomes an excellent potent ally in facing the demands of daily life with strength and vigor. In the form of herbal preparations, tinctures, or dietary supplements, Siberian ginseng becomes a revered botanical jewel, treasured for its potency to rejuvenate the body, uplift the soul, and strengthen its resilience in the face of life's many challenges.

vii). Schisandra (*Schisandra chinensis*):

Schisandra, *Schisandra chinensis*, referred to as Wu Wei Zi in the ancient Chinese and Russian herbal tradition, finds an honored place in the pantheon of botanical treasures. Native to the bountiful lands of China and Russia, this vine has long been regarded as a powerful tonic herb, renowned for its remarkable ability to boost vitality, enhance cerebral function, and strengthen resilience to stress [16]. At the center of Schisandra's therapeutic power lies a suite of bioactive compounds, the lignans, that orchestrate a symphony of adaptogenic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities [28]. Working together, these lignans bestow Schisandra with its valued adaptogenic power, assisting the body to adapt and buffer against the effects of stress.

Evidence suggests that Schisandra shows promise in modulating cortisol levels, the body's primary stress hormone, thereby facilitating emotional balance, elevating mood, and enhancing resistance to stress-induced fatigue [16]. Whether consumed as a soothing tea, potent tincture, or convenient dietary supplement, Schisandra stands as a versatile botanical support, offering reprieve from life's myriad challenges and fostering a state of harmony and vitality [16]. In other words, Schisandra emerges as a revered guardian of health and well-being, its holistic therapeutic properties offering consolation and fortitude to those traveling along life's complex winding paths.

viii). Licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*):

Derived from *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, licorice root has become one of the ingredients in traditional medicine, such as Ayurveda and TCM, due to its multiple and complex therapeutic properties. Known for being an adaptogen and anti-inflammatory agent, licorice has been used for ages to attain general health and fight many health-related problems. With adaptogenic capacity, licorice root helps better cope with stressors as it supports adrenal function [29]. The ability to modulate the response of the body to stress helps restore physiological balance, which is responsible for increasing the resilience and vitality of the body through restoration of physiological processes [29].

Licorice root's anti-inflammatory properties add value to its therapeutic power by helping alleviate symptoms through the reduction of inflammation. In this respect, it is effective particularly in regard to chronic inflammation conditions such as arthritis or gastrointestinal disorders. Licorice root helps in adrenal function and reducing stress-induced inflammation, thereby making it a natural remedy for general health and well-being, providing a holistic way in managing many health conditions [30].

ix). Reishi mushroom (*Ganoderma lucidum*):

Reishi mushroom, scientifically known as *Ganoderma lucidum* and commonly referred to as Lingzhi, is one of the best-known and highly treasured in traditional Chinese medicine because of the multifaceted health-benefiting actions it displays. Reishi mushroom is very adaptogenic in action and has been used for centuries to promote overall well-being and longevity. The adaptogenic properties of Reishi mushroom enable it to increase resistance to stress, thus helping the body cope better with multiple forms of stress. With the modulation of the body's stress response systems, Reishi mushroom restores physiological process balance and thereby supports mental and physical well-being [31].

In addition, Reishi mushroom is considered as an immunomodulatory potent herb, as it supports and regulates the immune system [31]. It is composed of biologically active substances such as polysaccharides, triterpenoids, and ganoderic acids, which are known to stimulate immune function and reduce inflammation [32]. With increased body defense mechanisms, Reishi mushroom supports the immune system, thereby promoting defense against pathogens and overall health maintenance. Also, its immunomodulatory properties may have been responsible for its anti-inflammatory properties, through which this herb influences inflammatory conditions in individuals. All these actions of Reishi mushroom make it an important natural therapeutic agent for increasing resilience, supporting immune health, and promoting longevity.

x). *Bacopa (Bacopa monnieri)*:

Bacopa, scientifically called *Bacopa monnieri* and popularly known as Brahmi, has taken a considerable place in Ayurvedic medicine due to its complex cognitive-enhancing properties. Traditionally used for centuries as a brain tonic, *Bacopa* is much recognized for its ability to improve memory, cognitive function, and overall mental performance [33]. Its adaptogenic nature empowers it to assist the body in the adaptation to stressors, thus increasing its resilience and mental clarity [33]. Moreover, its neuroprotective properties further augment its therapeutic effect, which will help in the prevention of age-related cognitive decline and neurodegenerative diseases.

Secondly, *Bacopa* contains bioactive compounds such as bacosides, which have been seen to have salubrious effects on health and brain [34]. Such compounds will escalate neuronal communication, increase cerebral blood flow, and support the growth of nerve cells in the brain. *Bacopa* will also promote synaptic plasticity and neurotransmitter function, which will enhance cognitive processes like learning, retention of memory, and information processing. Its neuroprotective properties also further help in minimizing oxidative stress, inflammation, and neuronal damage, adding to its positive effect on cognitive function and brain health [34]. In general, the adaptogenic and neuroprotective properties of *Bacopa* make it a herbal remedy that can be helpful in enhancing cognitive function, supporting mental performance, and fostering brain health.

xi). *Turmeric (Curcuma longa)*:

Traditionally derived from the flowering plant *Curcuma longa*, turmeric has been a staple in Southeast Asian Ayurvedic medicine for its myriad health benefits over the years. Traditionally, it has been known for its anti-inflammatory properties, which play a vital role in relieving several health conditions, hence boosting the overall well-being of the user. Along these lines, turmeric is also known to support the immune function, hence adding to its therapeutic potential regarding the fight against infections and bolstering the body's defense mechanisms [35]. Latest research, for instance, by Sanmukhani et al. 2013, has projected turmeric as a potential solution in dealing with mental health [36]. In fact, evidence shows that turmeric may reduce symptoms of depression and anxiety, thereby coming out as a natural, holistic cure to mental and emotional well-being [36]. All these recent researches focus on diverse therapeutic applications of turmeric apart from the traditional uses, thereby further highlighting its importance in terms of comprehensive health.

xii). *Cordyceps (Cordyceps sinensis)*:

Cordyceps is a product of the parasitic fungus *Cordyceps sinensis*, which is considered to be a medicinal fungus known for many centuries to Tibetan and Chinese medicine. These are grown in mountainous areas, especially in the Himalayas and other high-altitude places. Therefore, such a superfood has been in high demand due to its numerous health benefits. Other researches, such as the research by Hirsch et al. in 2012, have shown the potential of *Cordyceps* regarding health benefits [37]. Its health benefits include reducing fatigue, which has been described as a frequently reported complaint in modern human societies due to high-pressure lifestyles and a high level of stress [37]. *Cordyceps* can thus help increase energy and vitality levels of people to better cope with stresses from everyday life. In this way, *Cordyceps* can also offer even better performance in exercise and help athletes and fitness people in search of ergogenic agents, which may be helpful for optimal performance. This is complemented by *Cordyceps*' immune-boosting properties, whereby the body's natural defense mechanisms against infections and other agents that induce diseases are strengthened [38]. Through this adaptogenic effect, *Cordyceps* contributes to increasing the body's resilience against pathogens and other environmental risks, and therefore leads to enhanced health and wellbeing. These findings place the value of *Cordyceps* as a valuable adjunct, hence, further justify its value in enhancing physical endurance, immune health, and overall vitality, consolidating its status as a precious adaptogen of traditional medicine systems.

xiii). *Mongolian milkvetch (Astragalus mongholicus)*:

Astragalus mongholicus belongs to the legume family and is a perennial plant, native to the grasslands of Mongolia, China, and other parts of East Asia. *Astragalus mongholicus* has been an integral component of traditional Chinese medicine for hundreds of years, given its medicinal properties, and is known as "Huang Qi." Historically, *Astragalus mongholicus* has been valued for its adaptogenic and

immunomodulating properties, which have made it a very popular remedy for enhancing vitality and resilience [39]. Scientific studies have demonstrated that *Astragalus mongholicus* regulates immune function by stimulating the production of white blood cells, increasing the body's ability to fight off infections and diseases [40]. In addition, the plant is believed to possess anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, which constitute further therapeutic value in improving overall health and well-being.

xiv). Maral root (*Rhaponticum carthamoides*):

Rhaponticum carthamoides, also known as Russian Leuzea or Maral root, is a herbaceous perennial native to Siberia and parts of Central Asia, including Kazakhstan. In traditional Siberian folk medicine, *Rhaponticum carthamoides* has been used because of its purported adaptogenic effects, and a use as a tonic to enhance physical and mental performance [41]. It has been used in long-standing practice as a natural remedy against fatigue and improvement of endurance along with increasing overall vitality, especially among those engaged in arduous physical activities or exposed to environmental stressors [42]. Studies on *Rhaponticum carthamoides* promise its potential for increasing the physical work capacity and improving athletic performance and supporting recovery from demanding exercises. Further studies on *Rhaponticum carthamoides* suggest the presence of anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, further enhancing its therapeutic health and well-being benefits [41].

xv). Shatavari (*Asparagus racemosus*):

Shatavari, known scientifically as *Asparagus racemosus*, is a traditional medicinal herb that finds its origin in India and Sri Lanka and has been deeply embedded in the Ayurvedic tradition as a herb with a variety of health benefits. Shatavari has been traditionally used mainly for reproductive health, particularly for females, and also for restoring the balance of hormones. Its traditional uses include support of fertility, regularizing menstrual cycles, and relief of menopausal symptoms. Additionally, Shatavari has traditionally been valued for its adaptogenic properties that help in coping with stress, improving mood, and improving the general state of the well-being of individuals [43]. Kumari and Augusti conducted research that seems to point to Shatavari as a multivariate herbal remedy for providing holistic care for the health of women and emotional well-being based on the principles of Ayurveda [44]. Such findings point to Shatavari as a broad herbal remedy capable of providing holistic care for women's health and emotional well-being according to the principles of Ayurveda.

IV. SCIENTIFIC EVIDENCE FOR ADAPTOGENIC PLANTS IN MENTAL HEALTH

There has been growing interest in the potential of adaptogenic plants in the recent years to help manage symptoms of mental health disorders. This section deals with the current evidence in the scientific literature regarding the use of adaptogens in mental health, focusing on clinical studies, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, placebo-controlled trials, and comparisons with standard treatments.

IV.I Review of Clinical Studies Investigating the Efficacy of Adaptogens:

Clinical studies on adaptogenic plants in relation to their effects on mental health have given vital insights into their potentials for therapeutics. Among those adaptogens that have attracted maximum attention is ashwagandha, a drug in Ayurvedic medicine proven to be stress busters. A randomized controlled trial published in the Journal of Clinical Psychiatry studied the effects of ashwagandha to reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression in the case of patients with generalized anxiety disorder [18]. The results showed that the ashwagandha group was significantly better than the control group in reducing both anxiety and depression scores, thus proving to be an effective natural intervention for anxiety disorders [18].

Similarly to that, research on yet another popular adaptogen, *Rhodiola rosea*, has reported promising results. A systematic review published in Phytomedicine considered the effects of Rhodiola supplementation on mental fatigue, stress, and cognitive performance [45]. The review reported that Rhodiola extract may be beneficial for the improvement of cognitive function and mental well-being,

especially in the case of patients suffering from conditions related to mental fatigue under stress [45]. Similarly, a double-blind, placebo-controlled study studied the effectiveness of Rhodiola extract on alleviating depressive and emotional instability symptoms [21]. The findings showed significant improvements in mood and emotional well-being in the Rhodiola supplementation group, thus suggesting its use as a supplement in the treatment of depression.

Holy basil, commonly known as *Ocimum sanctum*, has also been investigated for its adaptogenic and anxiolytic properties. A randomized, placebo-controlled trial in the Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine looked at the impacts of holy basil supplementation on symptoms of generalized anxiety disorder [46]. The results of this study showed that holy basil supplementation was significantly associated with significant reductions in the symptoms of anxiety and in the overall quality of life when compared to placebo, thus proving to be an effective natural intervention for anxiety-related conditions.

IV.II Discussion of Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses:

Systematic reviews and meta-analyses provide ample source of comprehensive summaries on the efficacy of adaptogenic plants on mental health. One of the studies where a meta-analysis was conducted to determine if ginseng supplementation exerts a role in enhancing mood and cognitive performance was done by Reay et al. in 2005 [22]. This meta-analysis combined data from several randomized, placebo-controlled trials. The results indicated that supplementation with ginseng significantly enhanced mood and cognitive performance. The findings suggested that ginseng can be a potential candidate as a cognitive enhancer and mood stabilizer in healthy people.

A maca supplement was also looked into in relation to mental health in a systematic review published in BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine [47]. In the review, the data from various clinical trials were analyzed and stated that supplementation with maca exerted a positive effect on mood, especially in reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression. The findings, therefore, suggested that maca supplementation is efficient for an individual with mood disturbances or symptoms of stress.

IV.III Consideration of Placebo-Controlled Trials and Comparisons with Standard Treatments:

This is of utmost importance in proving the effects of treatment of adaptogenic plants through a placebo-controlled trial, since it helps find rigid proof of the plant product's therapeutic effect. Placebo-controlled trials help to diminish bias and confounding factors by aiding more accurate judgments of treatment effects. For example, a study by Hartz et al. (2004) aimed at studying the effectiveness of ginseng supplementation in reducing symptoms of depression among patients with chronic fatigue syndrome [48]. A significant reduction of the depression score was seen following ginseng supplementation, and these findings support its potential use as an adjunct in the treatment of depression.

Finally, it may be considered whether there are comparisons of adaptogenic plants against standard treatments to find out if adaptogenic plant supplements are as effective as standard treatments. It was conducted by a study by Cooley et al. in 2009, which compared the effects of the ashwagandha supplement to standard psychotherapy in patients suffering from anxiety disorders [49]. There was a finding of supplementation with ashwagandha being as effective as the standard psychotherapy in alleviating symptoms of anxiety. These results support the fact that the preparation has potential as an alternative or adjunct therapy for conditions characterized by anxiety.

The overall clinical study, systematic reviews, meta-analysis, placebo-controlled trials, and comparisons with the standard treatment present robust evidence in support of the effectiveness of adaptogenic plants in mental health. These studies show insights about the potential safety and effectiveness of adaptogens as natural interventions to relieve symptoms of stress, anxiety, depression, and other mental health disorders. Further studies are needed to explain the mechanism of action and further optimization of the therapeutic use of adaptogens in clinical settings.

Plant name Intervention/ control/ Daily dose/ Duration	Study design ^a / Total subjects	Primary endpoint and main results ^b	Quality level of evidence*	Jadad score [50]*	Reference
<i>Rhodiola rosea</i> Extract SHR-5 (288 mg twice daily)/placebo for 4 weeks	R, PC, DB 2 parallel groups 60 volunteers with stress-induced fatigue, (30/30) [20–55 years]	Symptoms of fatigue, attention, depression, QOL, salivary cortisol. Symptoms of fatigue, attention and salivary cortisol significantly improved compared with control	Ib	5	[51]
<i>Rhodiola rosea</i> Extract SHR-5 (170 mg once daily)/placebo for 2 weeks	R, PC, CO, DB 2 parallel groups 56 healthy subjects (??) ^c [24–35 years]	Mental fatigue, perceptive and cognitive functions such as associative thinking, short-term memory, calculation and ability of concentration, and speed of audio-visual perception Statistically significant improvement in the treatment group (SHR-5) during	Ib	4	[3]
<i>Rhodiola rosea</i> Extract SHR-5 (50 mg twice daily)/placebo for 20 days	R, PC, DB 2 parallel groups 40 healthy subjects (20/20) [17–19 years]	Mental fatigue, physical performance, general well-being Significant improvement in physical fitness, mental fatigue and neuromotor tests compared with control (p<0.01). General well-being was also significantly (p<0.05) better in the verum group. No sign	Ib	3	[52]
<i>Rhodiola rosea</i> Extract SHR-5 (single dose	R, PC, DB 3 parallel treatments	Capacity for mental work Significant difference in anti-fatigue effects in SHR-5	Ib	3	[3]
	groups 161 healthy subjects, (41/20/40 treated + 20 untreated) [19–21 years]	groups compared with control (p<0.001), whilst no significant difference between the two dosage groups was observed.			[3]
	R, PC, DB 3 parallel treatment groups 91 patients with mild and moderate depression (31/30/30) [18–70 years]	Depression in total HAMD and BDI scores Significant differences in HAMD and BDI scores and scores reflecting levels of insomnia, emotional instability, somatisation and self-esteem in SHR-5 groups compared to placebo (p<0.001)	Ib	5	[21]
<i>Eleutherococcus senticosus</i> Extract (2mg eleutherosides B and E equivalent to 2–4 g of herbal substance daily)/placebo for 2 months and 2 months of follow-up	R, PC, DB 2 parallel treatment groups 96 patients with chronic fatigue syndrome (49/47) [21–65 years]	RVI measurement of fatigue reduced Significant (p<0.05) improvement in RVI compared with control after 2 months treatment in the subgroups of patients with moderate fatigue at baseline (RVI value 8–12) and a history of fatigue <5 years. However, no signif	Ib	5	[3]

Chisan-fixed combination of Rhodiola-Schisandra-Eleutherococcus	R, PC, DB 2 parallel groups 60 patients suffering from acute non-specific pneumonia (30/30) [18–65 years]	Duration of antibiotic therapy associated with the clinical manifestations of the acute phase of the disease, mental performance and self-evaluation by WHO-QOL brief questionnaires Adjuvant therapy with ADAPT-232 had a positive effect on the recovery of p	Ib	4	[3]
ADAPT-232 capsules [fixed combination of standardised extracts of <i>Rhodiola rosea</i> (salidroside 3 mg), <i>E. senticosus</i> (syringin 3 mg), <i>S. chinensis</i> (schizandrin 4 mg)] 3 capsules acute	PC, CO, DB 60 PC, CO, DB 5 cosmonauts	Compared with placebo, ADAPT-232 significantly increased short-term memory, speed and reliability in the understanding of information, and precision and accuracy in the ability to reproduce the information in repeated highly sophisticated computer-based t	IIa IIa	1	[3]
<i>Eleutherococcus senticosus</i> extract 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 4.0 and 8.0 mL acute	PC, CO, OL 357 Sailors	<i>E. senticosus</i> improved mental performance in correction test; increased activity of the adrenal cortex, the activity of the sympathetic adrenomedullar system, the intensity of metabolic processes, and the intensity of red-ox processes. In stress conditions	IIa	1	[3]
<i>Schisandra chinensis</i> extract 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 4.0 and 8.0 mL acute		<i>S. chinensis</i> stimulated the activity of the CNS at night; increased tonus of the sympathetic part of the autonomic nervous system (having no effect on the parasympathetic part) after night duty; activated the adrenal cortex activity; increased the activity	-	-	-
<i>Rhodiola rosea</i> (extract) 10 drops or 3 x 10 drops/day <i>Rhaponticum cartamoides</i> (extract) 40 drops or 3 x 10 drops/day. Acute and 10 days	PC, SB 80 healthy students (control group) and 70 patients with neurosis	Single and repeated administration of adaptogens improved functional state of the CNS in patients with neurosis as characterised by normalisation of the speed and power of neural processes in Ivanov-Smolenski's verbal test with speech-supported locomotor-	IIa	1	[3]
Rhododin (<i>R. rosea</i> extract, 100 mg/ 20 days	PC, DB 60	Significant improvement in physical fitness, mental fatigue and neuromotor tests compared	IIa	1	[3]

		with control ($p < 0.01$): general well-being was also significantly ($p < 0.05$) better in the verum group. No significance was seen in the correction of text tests or a ne			
Rodelim tablets (fixed combination of the extracts of <i>R. rosea</i> , <i>E. senticosus</i> and <i>S. chinensis</i>) 100 mg/acute	PC, DB 60	Rodelim improved mental working capacity in computer and correction tests against a background of fatigue.	IIa	1	[53]
<i>R. rosea</i> (tincture 40% ethanol) 5-10 drops/acute	PC/85	Improved mental performance, reduced the number of errors in Anfimov's correction test: the stimulating effect lasted 4 h or more	IIb	1	[3]
<i>Rhodiola rosea</i> (40% ethanol tincture, 20 drops) <i>E. senticosus</i> (40% ethanol tincture, 20 drops) Extract of <i>R. rosearhizome</i> , 0.3 g/ acute	PC/254	Improved mental performance; reduced the number of errors in Anfimov's correction test; increased the accuracy, working capacity and speed of information perception. Stimulating effect lasted 4 h or more	IIa	1	[3]
Tyrosol (1, 5, 10 and 20 mg), <i>R. rosea</i> extract, 5 drops	? / 82 patients	Improved mental performance, reduced the number of errors in Anfimov's correction test.	III	0	[3]
Salidroside, 2.5 mg/ acute	PC, SB/ 46	Improved mental performance; reduced the number of errors in Anfimov's correction test; stimulating effect lasting 4 h or more.	IIa	1	[27]
<i>E. senticosus</i> (dry extract), 120 mg/ Acute and 3 weeks	PC, DB/40	Improved mental performance determined by a letter correction test	IIa	1	
<i>E. senticosus</i> (tincture) <i>P. ginseng</i> tincture/ 2 ml/ acute	PC, SB,CO/ 13	Decreased errors in data sent by radio operators 1 h after drug uptake. Stimulating effect of <i>E. senticosus</i> was stronger and more stable than the effect of Ginseng, which was insignificant.	IIa	1	[3]
<i>Eleutherococcus</i> (extract 1250 mg) Ginkgo (extract, 28 mg flavonoids, 7 mg ginkgolides) 3 months	PC, CO /24	Selective memory significantly improved compared with placebo ($p < 0.02$).	IIa	1	[3]
<i>S. chinensis</i> (tincture) <i>E. senticosus</i> (tincture) <i>Rhaponticum cartamoides</i> (tincture) <i>Oplopanax elatus</i> (tincture), 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 mL, acute	PC, CO, OL 1327 healthy subjects	<i>Eleutherococcus</i> and <i>Rhaponticum</i> treatment significantly increased precision in tremometric test compared with placebo. Significant differences compared with placebo were observed with various doses of all tested preparations in psychometric tests includin	IIa	1	

<i>S. chinensis</i> (tincture) <i>E. senticosus</i> (tincture) <i>Rhaponticum cartamoides</i> (tincture) <i>Oplopanax elatus</i> (tincture, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 mL), 10 days	PC, CO 665 healthy subjects	Pilots were tested before a flight and again 5 –15 min later, and finally 1 and 3 h after landing Significant differences compared with placebo were observed for all tested preparations in tests including assessment of precision, dynamic tremometry, senso	IIa	1	[3]
<i>S. chinensis</i> (tincture, 2 ml) <i>E. senticosus</i> (tincture, 2 ml) Coffee, 200 ml Black tea, 200 ml (control) Acute and repeated	OL, PC 200 sailors	<i>S. chinensis</i> showed a tonic effect for 4–7 h in those on night duties. <i>E. senticosus</i> was inactive Repeated uptake (for more than 2 weeks) of coffee and <i>S. chinensis</i> produced similar negative effects (insomnia, excitability, etc.).	IIb	0	[3]
<i>S. chinensis</i> (seed powder, 2g) <i>Panax ginseng</i> (tincture, 2 ml), acute	CO, PC, SB, 122 students	Improved attention in text correction 2 h after drug administration. Both extracts increased quality and quantity of mental work performed.	IIa	1	[54]
<i>S. chinensis</i> (seed tincture, 30 ml) <i>P. ginseng</i> (3% tincture, 30 ml) Phenamine (0.02 g) Glucose (0.5 g), acute	CO, PC /20	<i>P. ginseng</i> and <i>S. chinensis</i> improved accuracy in the work of telegraph operators at exhaustion compared with control group (glucose) and those given phenamine.	IIa	1	[3]
<i>S. chinensis</i> (seed – 3 g, extract and fractions, tablets and capsules, 0.036–0.168 g), acute	OL, CO/20	Improved accuracy in error correction test. Most active stimulating effect was revealed by a crystalline substance identified as the lignan schizandrin.	IIb	0	[3]
Schizandrin (0.02, 0.01, 0.005 g), Phenamine (0.2 g) Glucose (0.5g) acute	PC/23	Schizandrin improved accuracy in the work of telegraph operators at exhaustion compared with control group (glucose) and those given phenamine.	IIb	1	[3]
<i>S. chinensis</i> (seed powder, 0.25 and 0.5 g), 10 days	OL / 36	Beneficial effects on symptoms of astheno-depressive syndrome	IIIa	0	[55]
<i>S. chinensis</i> (fruit and seed tincture, 1:5, 90% ethanol, 1 ml), 16–40 days	OL/ 40	Stimulating effect-improve mood, increases physical and psychological vivacity, relief of tiredness and fatigue in asthenia and depressions.	III	0	[3]
<i>S. chinensis</i> (tincture, decoction and tablets), 2–10 weeks	OL/ 2000	Stimulating and tonic effect.	III	0	[3]
<i>S. chinensis</i> (tincture, decoction and tablets), 2–10 weeks	OL/ 250	Effective in the treatment of general asthenia, exhaustion and reduced physical and mental performance in group of patients with nervous disorders where an increase in general well-being	III	0	[56]

		and working capacity, as well as a decrease in sleepiness and exhaus			
<i>S. chinensis</i> (tincture 95%) 45–120 drops <i>S. chinensis</i> (tablets, 0.25 g, 0.5 g),10 days	OL, observational study/ 30	Stimulating effect in astheno-depressive syndrome with relief of somnolence, limpness, tiredness, fatigue	III	0	[3]

Table 1: Results of clinical studies on humans involving effects of plant adaptogens on physical and mental performance related to fatigue. (^a R – Randomized, PC – placebo– controlled; DB – double– blind; SB – single blind, NC – not controlled; CO – crossover, UC – uncontrolled, OL – open label trial; ^b According to WHO, FDA and EMEA: Ia – meta– analyses of randomised and controlled studies; Ib – evidence from at least one randomised study with control ; IIa – evidence from at least one well– performed study with control group; IIb – evidence from at least one well– performed quasi– experimental study; III – evidence from well– performed non– experimental descriptive studies as well as comparative studies, correlation studies and case– studies; and IV – evidence from expert committee reports or appraisals and/or clinical experiences by prominent authorities; ^c ? – data not listed or unavailable.* –max 5.)

V. MECHANISMS OF ACTION OF ADAPTOGENIC PLANTS

Adaptogenic plants are thought to promote good mental health and resilience to stress due to various biophysical mechanisms. The primary mechanisms involve modulation of the body's stress response systems and promotion of neuroprotective and anti-inflammatory processes.

V.I Biological and Physiological mechanisms

Adaptogen mechanisms of action are mediated through biological and physiological interactions between the stress response systems and the neuroendocrine pathways within the body. Adaptogens modulate the activity of several signaling molecules, including neurotransmitters, hormones, and cytokines, to promote homeostasis and enhance resilience to stress [20]. Multitargeted action of these botanical agents means that they exert their influence over many cellular pathways in order to achieve the therapeutic effects.

V.II Impact on the Stress Response System:

One of the most important mechanisms of action for adaptogens is their ability to regulate the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, which in turn is the central stress response system in the human body. Adaptogens are said to help normalize the HPA axis, reducing excessive production of stress hormones like cortisol while enhancing the capacity of the body to muster an appropriate response to a stressful stimulus [3].

This regulation of the HPA axis is thought to underlie many of the adaptogenic effects, such as improved stress tolerance, reduced fatigue, and enhanced mental and physical performance. Adaptogens are thought to accomplish this through interaction with a variety of signaling pathways and transcription factors, such as heat shock proteins, stress-activated kinases, and forkhead box O (FoxO) proteins [57]. The hypothetical mechanism of action of adaptogens on the stress system is shown in Fig. 1 [58].

Fig 1: Hypothetical mechanism of action of adaptogens on the stress system.

V.III Neuroprotective, Anti-inflammatory, and Antioxidant Properties

Adaptogenic plants have neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties, which confer resilience to stress and attenuation from stress-related damage. Biologically active substances, such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and terpenoids found in these botanical agents, act to enhance the protective

effects of antioxidants by scavenging free radicals and reducing oxidative stress [3]. Adaptogens mitigate oxidative stress and inflammation in the brain, thereby maintaining neuronal function and enhancing neuroplasticity, with the resultant enhancement of cognitive function and emotional well-being [55].

Adaptogenic plants also exert inflammatory modulation by decreasing the pro-inflammatory cytokines' biosynthesis and inhibiting inflammatory signal transduction pathways, and thereby neuroinflammation is dampened, and the effect of chronic inflammation on mental health is reduced [3]. Further to this, adaptogenic plants help prevent neurodegenerative diseases and mitigate age-related decline in cognitive function, probably through their anti-inflammatory mechanism of action.

In summary, adaptogenic plants have a multifaceted mechanism of action of amelioration of stress response systems, neuroprotective pathways, and inflammatory processes. In this way, adaptogens augment stress resistance, enhance mental health, and protect against chronic stress-induced detrimental effects on cognitive function and emotional health. Further research is needed to elucidate specific mechanisms of action for various adaptogens and to optimize their therapeutic use in clinical practice.

VI. SAFETY AND POTENTIAL SIDE EFFECTS OF ADAPTOGENS

Since adaptogenic plants are usually considered safe, it is cautious, in terms of their safety profile, possible interaction with drugs, and possible adverse effects, to assess its use in clinical practice and self-care regimens. The safety profile, potential interactions with medications and adverse effects of some adaptogenic plants is listed below in Table 2.

Adaptogenic Plant	Safety Profile	Potential Interactions with Medications	Adverse Effects	References
Ashwagandha (<i>Withania somnifera</i>)	Generally well-tolerated but may cause mild gastrointestinal upset or allergic reactions in some Individuals	May Interact with Immunosuppressants, sedatives and medications used to lower blood sugar levels.	Rare adverse effects may include drowsiness, headache, or nausea	[18]
Rhodiola (<i>Rhodiola rosea</i>)	Generally safe when used as directed, but may cause mild side effects such as dizziness dry mouth, or Insomnia in some individuals	May Interact with antidepressants anticoagulants, and medications used to treat diabetes	Rare adverse effects may Include agitation, irritability or palpitations.	[45]
Holy Basil (<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>)	Generally safe for most Individuals when consumed as a culinary herb or used in moderate doses	There is limited information on potential interactions but caution is advised when using concurrently with medications that may affect blood sugar levels or blood pressure	Rare adverse effects may Include Gastrointestinal discomfort or allergic reactions	[46]
Ginseng (<i>Panax ginseng</i>)	Generally well-tolerated but may cause headaches, insomnia, or gastrointestinal upset in some individuals	May interact with anticoagulants, antidiabetic medications, and medications metabolized by the cytochrome P450 enzyme system	Rare adverse effects may include hypertension palpitations, or manic episodes	[22]

Maca (<i>Lepidium meyenil</i>)	Generally well-tolerated but may cause mild gastrointestinal upset or allergic reactions in some Individuals	Limited information on potential interactions, but caution is advised when using concurrently with medications that may affect hormone levels or blood pressure.	Rare adverse effects may include Insomnia, mood changes, or menstrual Irregularities	[47]
Siberian Ginseng (<i>Eleutherococcus senticosus</i>)	Generally well-tolerated but may cause mild gastrointestinal upset or Insomnia in some Individuals	May interact with anticoagulants, antidiabetic medications, and medications metabolized by the cytochrome P450 enzyme system	Rare adverse effects may include hypertension palpitations, or nervousness	[3]
Schisandra (<i>Schisandra chinensis</i>)	Generally safe when used as directed, but may cause mild gastrointestinal upset or allergic reactions in some Individuals	Limited information on potential interactions, but caution is advised when using concurrently with medications that may affect liver function or blood pressure.	Rare adverse effects may include dizziness headache, or skin rash	[58]

Table 2: The safety profile, potential interactions with medications, and adverse effects of some adaptogenic plants.

VII. FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND CHALLENGES

Future directions and challenges of knowledge as herbal remedies, particularly adaptogenic plants, for mental health gain interest, mechanisms of actions, optimal dosing, and long-term effects remain to be investigated. Standardization and quality control are set, to establish quality production consistency and safety. Standardization and quality control measures should be put in place for the development of policies to oversee production and marketing. Integrating herbal therapies into mainstream mental health care, however, is hindered by a lack of awareness among the healthcare and medical communities. This is a challenge that requires ongoing education and cooperation to fully realize the potential of herbal remedies in mental well-being. The future directions and challenges of herbal remedies for mental health disorders are listed below in Table 3.

i). **Standardization and Quality Control:** One of the major challenges in the use of adaptogenic plants is the lack of standardized preparations and quality control measures. It is necessary to standardize extraction methods and ensure the quality of the products with stringent testing protocols for better reproducibility and reliability of research studies [3]. This will require collaborative efforts among researchers, regulatory agencies, and stakeholders in the industry to agree upon standards of quality and encourage transparency in the production and distribution of adaptogenic products [59].

ii). **Mechanistic Understanding:** Although mounting evidence supports the efficacy of adaptogenic plants, the exact mechanisms underlying their therapeutic efficacy are not yet fully elucidated. Mechanistic studies at the molecular, cellular, and pharmacological levels will be important for elucidating how adaptogens may exert their beneficial effects on stress resilience, cognitive function, and emotional well-being [20]. Pharmacological, biochemical, and systems biology approaches offer promising tools for unveiling the complex mechanisms of action of adaptogenic plants [16].

iii). **Clinical Validation:** Despite the abundance of preclinical and anecdotal evidence supporting the use of adaptogenic plants, large-scale clinical trials are needed to confirm their efficacy and safety across diverse populations. Well-designed randomized controlled trials with standardized endpoints and rigorous methodology are needed to provide high-level evidence of the clinical efficacy of adaptogens in the management of mental health disorders and promotion of overall well-being [58]. Collaboration between

academia, industry, and healthcare providers can help in designing and implementing clinical trials to address key research questions and guide evidence-informed practice [59].

iv). **Personalized Medicine:** Personalized medicine, fitted according to individual genetic, physiological, and lifestyle factors, is promising for the optimal therapeutic use of adaptogenic plants. With the use of genomic medicine, metabolomics, and technologies in digital health, scientists can identify biomarkers of response to adaptogens and spell out a strategy for individualized treatment of people with specific health needs or genetic susceptibility [58]. Integration of personalized approaches in clinical practice can advance treatment efficacy, minimize the adverse effects, and improve the results for patients.

v). **Regulatory Frameworks:** Developing clear regulatory frameworks and guidelines for assessing, registering, and marketing adaptogenic products is paramount to ensuring consumer safety and quality assurance. The regulation agencies have to set standards on the labeling of products, recommendations for dosage, and follow-up on safety to ensure public safety [3]. International harmonization of regulatory requirements and cooperation would enhance the accessibility of safe and effective adaptogenic products while at the same time preventing the spread of substandard or adulterated formulations.

In conclusion, though adaptogenic plants are promising as natural interventions in promoting resilience to stress and supporting mental well-being, the key challenges to be addressed include standardization, mechanistic understanding, clinical validation, personalized medicine, and regulatory frameworks to realize their full therapeutic potential and evidence-based practice in integrative healthcare.

Future Directions	Challenges	Reference
Further Research on Mechanisms of Action	Limited Understanding of Mechanisms: Despite their widespread use, the precise mechanisms of action of adaptogenic plants remain incompletely understood. Future research should focus on elucidating the molecular pathways and biological processes underlying their therapeutic effects.	[58]
Clinical Trials for Specific Conditions	Lack of Rigorous Clinical Trials: While preliminary evidence supports the efficacy of adaptogens for various health conditions, more high-quality, placebo-controlled clinical trials are needed to establish their effectiveness, safety, and optimal dosing regimens for specific populations and conditions.	[49][18]
Standardization of Products	Lack of Standardization: i). Variability in the composition and quality of adaptogenic products poses challenges in ensuring consistency and efficacy. Standardization of herbal preparations, including the identification and quantification of bioactive compounds, is essential for quality control and reproducibility.	[3]
Exploration of Novel Adaptogens	Identification of New Compounds: Continued exploration of novel adaptogenic plants and bioactive compounds may uncover new therapeutic agents with unique mechanisms of action and improved efficacy for addressing specific health concerns.	[60]
Integration into Mainstream Healthcare	Limited Integration into Healthcare: Despite their long history of traditional use, adaptogenic plants are often overlooked or dismissed in mainstream healthcare settings. Overcoming barriers such as lack of awareness, regulatory challenges, and cultural biases is crucial for integrating adaptogens into evidence-based healthcare practices.	[3][22]

Table 3: Future directions and Challenges.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, adaptogenic plants hold great promise to be therapeutic agents for mental health disorders and the same promise has been substantiated by a burgeoning body of literature. For example, clinical studies showed that adaptogens like ashwagandha, Rhodiola,

and holy basil significantly improved symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression, with favorable safety profiles and limited side effects. These botanical remedies act through diverse mechanisms, including modulation of stress response systems, neuroprotective effects, and anti-inflammatory mechanisms. Summarizing, adaptogenic plants represent added value for mental health disorders' treatment, offering natural alternatives to synthetic pharmacotherapeutic agents with the promise of fewer side effects and greater availability. Future studies should focus on elucidating more detail about the mechanisms of action, the best regimens of administrations, and the standardization of extracts and dosage forms. The promise of herbal remedies in the treatment of mental health disorders portends an expanded choice of treatment and a vast number of improved outcomes for millions of people in the world.

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